

On the Limitations of Hand-Engineered PPG Features for Hypertension Classification: Evidence from the VitalDB Subset of PulseDB

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Abstract

Photoplethysmography (PPG) has been widely used for cuffless blood pressure estimation and hypertension detection, yet no consensus exists regarding a standard set of discriminant PPG features. This study evaluates whether (1) an extensive feature space or (2) a clinically validated subset of commonly used PPG features can reliably distinguish hypertensive and healthy segments using only PPG signals. Experiments were conducted on the VitalDB-derived subset of the PulseDB database, which comprises 465,480 waveform segments. After signal pre-processing, 183 hand-engineered time-domain, frequency-domain, and derivative-based features were extracted in the first trial and reduced via correlation and variance filtering. The second trial employed 28 clinically supported features associated with blood pressure.

After an evaluation of a logistic regression and a random forest classifier, both approaches yielded limited balanced accuracy (≈ 0.64 – 0.71) and demonstrated substantial overlap between classes despite extensive feature engineering and model tuning. Visual inspection of waveform morphology suggested structural differences between the classes which were not captured. These findings indicate that discriminative PPG characteristics for hypertension may be dataset-specific and that universally optimal hand-engineered feature sets are difficult to establish. The results highlight the limitations of fixed feature pipelines and suggest that dataset-adaptive strategies or end-to-end representation learning may be required for robust PPG-based hypertension classification.

1 Introduction

1.1 Hypertension and Photoplethysmography

Hypertension, commonly linked to old age, genetics, low physical activity, diet of high salt content, and unhealthy lifestyles, is a cardiovascular condition where the pressure in blood vessels are high. It is associated with the most deadly causes of death and impacts approximately 1.4 billion adults between 30 and 79 years worldwide in 2024 [1]. The 2 metrics frequently used to assess a person’s overall cardiovascular state are the systolic blood pressure (SBP), the pressure in blood vessels at the peak of a systole, and the diastolic blood pressure (DBP), the pressure in the blood vessels at the trough of a diastole. These 2 values are usually derived from the arterial blood pressure (ABP) waveform signal measured continuously by a medical apparatus. There are different levels of severity of hypertension: a healthy segment has $SBP < 120$ mmHg (but above 90 mmHg) and $DBP < 80$ mmHg (but above 60 mmHg), elevated blood pressure is indicated by SBP between 120 mmHg and 129 mmHg, type 1 hypertension is defined as having SBP from 130 mmHg to 139 mmHg and DBP from 80 mmHg to 89 mmHg, and type 2 hypertension is defined as having SBP

> 140 mmHg and $DBP > 90$ mmHg [2]. This study focuses on differentiating type 2 hypertensive segments with the rest of the blood pressure groups.

As blood is pumped to and away from certain sections of a blood vessel, the blood vessel expands and contracts due to this change in internal blood volume. This marginal but measurable difference in vessel size changes how the vessel interacts with light, so when light is shone onto the blood vessel, different intensity of light is reflected back to a photodetector. By measuring this change over time, this idea, called photoplethysmography (PPG), effectively estimates pulses in blood vessels. The scope of this study is whether PPG alone can be used to estimate blood pressure and identify cases of hypertension, since after all, PPG is an indirect way of measuring cardiovascular activity compared to ABP, which is more direct [3]. Specifically, it identifies challenges in establishing a generalizable set of hand-engineered features that can be applied to all available PPG datasets.

1.2 Literature review

There are numerous studies focusing on detecting various heart diseases via different bio-signals. [4] uses the ECG waveform from the UCI Machine Learning Repository to identify abnormal segments using traditional machine learning algorithms and a simple artificial neural network (ANN). While [5] does not directly work with bio-signals, they utilize the SBP and DBP metrics derived from ABP, alongside other time-series data, to build a logistic regression classifier. [6] fed electromyography (EMG) features, extracted from data collected from Chungnam National University Hospital, into an LSTM algorithm to detect stroke. [7] uses a CNN-BiLSTM architecture to detect cardiac arrhythmia via ECG signals and yielded approximately 99.4% accuracy, precision, and recall. [8] also implements a CNN-LSTM and CNN-BiLSTM architecture, but it predicts stroke with electroencephalography (EEG). [9] trained a semi-supervised LSTM for a multi-class classification using heart rate data of subjects performing different daily activities while wearing a smartwatch. There is even a unique approach to determine blood pulses by measuring the sound reverberating from the earlobe [10].

Various studies have implemented AI-based pipelines to extract information from PPG signals, either through manual feature extraction or an end-to-end methodology. [11] designed a deep learning architecture utilizing a convolutional neural network (CNN), a long short-term memory (LSTM) layer, and a dense layer to detect important PPG features for atrial fibrillation detection. Although deep learning, notorious for its lack of interpretability, is foundational to the work, by implementing a CNN, the architecture not only yielded a superior performance, but it can also be visualized. In essence, each layer captured certain information that can be visually expressed and thus interpreted. [12] combines ECG and PPG signals to build various traditional machine learning models and deep learning architectures involving LSTM, yielding the highest accuracy of 99.15% using CNN-LSTM. [13] proposes a two-stage architecture involving a feature extractor and a feature aggregator to predict cardiac arrest in real time. [14] sets up a cloud computing-based system that sends data to a medical professional if the AI-based predictor stored in the cloud receives a PPG segment which suggests hypertension. [15] performs Grid Search on a CNN-LSTM model trained on PPG signals of the MIMIC-III dataset to fit a regression for the ABP signal, thereby deducing the SBP and DBP of the segment, ultimately satisfying medical standards for blood pressure prediction like the Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation (AAMI), the British Hypertension Society (BHS), and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). [16] processes PPG signals to visual plots from which atrial fibrillation risk can be calculated. [17], recognizing that ECG possesses information not present in PPG, builds a generative adversarial network (GAN) with attention to transform PPG signals to ECG, ultimately reducing a substantial amount of heart rate regression error. Similarly, [18] reconstructs ABP signal from PPG signal,

allowing a more direct measurement of blood pressure. Additionally, the author proposes a system which secures user data when implemented in a real-world setting. [19] implements an architecture which includes a CNN, 2 LSTM layers, and a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) to estimate blood pressure against the ground truths SBP and DBP provided by the ABP in the MIMIC-II database. This pipeline passed both the AAMI and BHS standards. [20] uses the MIMIC-III database and an end-to-end Transformer Encoder architecture to estimate ABP and blood oxygen saturation from PPG, acquiring lower error than prior research. [21] designs a preprocessing, feature extraction, and feature optimization pipeline which allows simple machine learning models estimate blood pressure given PPG, achieving a grade A for the BHS standard and meeting the AAMI standard. [22] shows that combining CNN-BiLSTM and attention to predict SBP and DBP from PPG achieves a high performance on the MIMIC-II database. [23] proposes a deep neural network to also predict SBP and DBP from PPG signal of the MIMIC-II database and also satisfies both the BHS and AAMI standards.

[24] summarizes ways in which the PPG signal is processed to remove noise, including scenarios with and without acceleration data. [25] synthesizes PPG processing techniques in general. [26] summarizes PPG features commonly associated with blood pressure.

1.3 Objectives and Structure

Prior research deviates in extracting different PPG features before machine learning. There have been several literature on aggregating frequently used features [26, 27], but there exists no exact standard on what features should be considered [25]. Meanwhile, some studies are borrowing features from others to maintain consistency [23]. This calls for research on whether providing a standard set of discriminant features for all PPG waveform data is feasible.

This study tests the generalizability of previously used features in blood pressure estimation with PPG on the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB Database.

The following section presents information on the dataset used in this study, the data preprocessing techniques applied, 2 trials of feature extraction that attempt to separate hypertensive and healthy segments, and the classification results for each trial. The following section will analyze these results, which leads to the final section, which states that each dataset requires close examination of its structure to determine that dataset’s specific optimal features. The article concludes with a discussion of the implications of this observation and recommending future research directions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dataset

This study uses PPG signals collected from the VitalDB dataset which is processed and provided as a subset in the larger PulseDB dataset. The PulseDB dataset is derived from two other prominent datasets [28], MIMIC-III Waveform Database Matched Subset and VitalDB. The MIMIC-III Waveform Database Matched Subset is the subset aggregated from the MIMIC-III Waveform Database and MIMIC-III Clinical Database such that only subjects with both physiological signals and clinical recordings available are included. Specifically, it contains 22317 waveform recordings (ECG, PPG, ABP, etc. [29]) and 22247 numerical records (demographics, laboratory test results, diagnostic results, etc. [30]) of 10282 different patients from intensive care units (ICUs) [31]. The VitalDB dataset contains waveform and numerical data from 6388 patients from the Seoul National University Hospital. Each waveform data was sampled at 500 Hz, and each numerical data was recorded once per 1 to 7 seconds, totaling more than 557000 tracks before 486451 were kept via quality

check [32]. In the PulseDB dataset, the 500 Hz sampling frequency of the waveform signals were downsampled to 125 Hz to ensure consistency with the MIMIC-III Matched Subset [28].

The author of [28] also provides a supplementary subset that has a more accessible computer storage requirement. Given the physical constraints of this article, the focus will be on this supplementary subset dataset, which is derived from the VitalDB section of the overarching dataset and is available on Kaggle [33]. According to [28], the VitalDB-derived Kaggle dataset downloaded includes 3 channels of waveform data: ECG, PPG, and ABP. Since this paper focuses on classifying hypertension using only PPG bio-signals, the PPG channel is extracted from the overall dataset. Additionally, since this dataset also includes metadata, two of which being SBP and DBP, by applying a threshold, each segment could be labeled as either "healthy" or "hypertensive," according to the definition of hypertension. In the documentation of the supplementary subset dataset, there are 5 data files. The data file used in this article is called "VitalDB_Train_Subset.mat". In total, there are 465480 segments (416434 healthy, 49046 hypertensive), each corresponding to one sample in the feature matrix to be constructed in the upcoming sections. Figure 1 displays an example of bio-signal segments of a random sample.

Figure 1: Preview of ECG, PPG, and ABP signals from record number 30.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

Figure 2 summarizes the data preprocessing pipeline for each PPG segment for the entire dataset. The preprocessing stage includes 5 main steps: anti-alias low-pass filtering, resampling, bandpass filtering, smoothing, and standardization.

All signals were resampled to 100 Hz from 125 Hz [28] using SciPy’s implementation of polyphase rational-factor resampling, which performs anti-alias filtering automatically before changing the

sampling rate. This anti-aliasing feature guarantees that no frequency distortion or aliasing is introduced during the conversion to a lower sampling frequency.

Figure 2: Overview of the data preprocessing pipeline applied to PPG signals.

After undersampling, a 3rd-order Butterworth band-pass filter with zero-phase forward-backward filtering and a frequency range of 0.5-8 Hz was applied to each PPG segment. This type of band-pass filter was used to maintain the inherent frequency structure of the PPG (no ripple) while excluding motion artifacts and frequency components considered abnormally high compared to a conventional PPG signal [25]. The Butterworth band-pass filtering method has also been implemented by various other literatures [24, 21, 20, 17]. A zero-phase forward-backward filter is included to remove unwanted frequency components from a signal without causing any phase distortion or time delay. This ensures that the PPG peaks, notches, and timing intervals remain physiologically accurate, allowing the model to learn consistent waveform dynamics. Regarding the chosen frequency range, while [34] cites the range 0.5-5 Hz as normal for PPG signals, [25] states that a strict frequency range for PPG has not been established and that a frequency below 15 Hz is acceptable. In fact, recent research has utilized a wider band than 0.5-5 Hz, highlighting that important morphological components of the PPG waveform, such as dicrotic notch, reflective waves, and higher-order harmonics, extend beyond 5 Hz. [24] recommends a variety of passbands (0.5-6 Hz, 0.5-10 Hz, 0.8-5 Hz, 0.3-5 Hz), depending on different PPG processing techniques; [20] uses a passband of 0.5-8 Hz; [17] uses a passband of 1-8 Hz; [23] uses a passband of 0-8 Hz; and [21] uses a passband of

0.5-12 Hz.

Then, a Savitzky–Golay smoothing filter – using an 11-sample window and a 2nd-order polynomial – was applied to each bandpass-filtered PPG segment to smooth high-frequency noise while preserving the morphology of the underlying waveform, which is important for the 1st derivative (velocity plethysmogram, VPG) and 2nd derivative (acceleration plethysmogram, APG) of the PPG [35, 36], both of which will be extracted after the preprocessing stage.

Finally, each smoothed PPG segment was normalized using Z-score standardization, defined as subtracting the mean of the segment and dividing by its standard deviation. This step ensures that all segments are transformed to have zero mean and unit variance, allowing machine learning models to focus on the shape of the waveform rather than its absolute amplitude, which can vary due to sensor placement, skin tone, or perfusion differences.

The following sections detail two trials of feature extraction and processing. Specifically, the next section assesses a feature-oriented approach to the classification of hypertension, whereby the various features of the PPG waveform were extracted extensively and reduced by correlation and variance before prediction. The subsequent section focuses on features that are clinically related to the measurement of blood pressure. By analyzing the feature distribution and the inherent structure of the dataset, these sections will explain why establishing a universal set of discriminant, manually selected features is not feasible for hypertension classification with PPG bio-signal.

2.3 Extensive exploration of feature space

2.3.1 Feature extraction

The first approach to generating the feature matrix on which machine learning models will be trained is to extract an extensive set of features and to subsequently reduce dimensionality through statistical methods. The feature extraction pipeline is summarized in Figure 3. Features were computed across both time-domain (which includes per-cycle features and cycle-to-cycle features) and frequency-domain, yielding an initial set of 183 features, including PPG and its derivatives, VPG and APG. Figure 4 illustrates an example of the result of Fast Fourier Transform applied on the PPG signal of a random sample. Figure 5 displays an example of Power Spectral Density analysis of the PPG signal of the same sample. Figure 6 shows an example of the PPG, VPG, and APG signals of a random sample together.

Previous works demonstrate that PPG-based blood pressure prediction is based on morphological, temporal, derivative, and spectral characteristics of the waveform. However, a standard feature set has not been established, as reported features vary significantly across studies. For example, following [37], [23] extracts 59 time-domain features of PPG, VPG, and APG while [21] extracts 40 time-domain features in addition to 6 frequency-domain features. [27] summarizes 13 most commonly used morphological details of the PPG signal, but several other works utilize a wider range of features, including the ratio between these morphological characteristics. Additionally, when [23] referenced the 59 features from [37], the authors noted that differences in the dataset may introduce discrepancies in the effectiveness of those 59 features, indicating the non-universal characteristic of PPG-based features.

Therefore, an exhaustive feature extraction stage was first implemented to cover the union of features reported in prior literature. Essentially, any applicable feature that can be derived was computed, resulting in 183 features as summarized in Table 1.

Figure 3: Pipeline for the comprehensive exploration of feature space.

Figure 4: Fast Fourier Transform applied on PPG record number 21.

Figure 5: Power Spectral Density analysis of PPG record number 21.

Figure 6: PPG, VPG, and APG of record number 13.

Table 1: Details of extracted features from PPG signal, VPG (1st derivative), and APG (2nd derivative)

Feature	Definition
PPG Aggregated Time-Domain Features (mean/std/median) – 57 features	
1. $mean_t_{cycle}$	Mean cycle duration
2. std_t_{cycle}	Standard deviation of cycle duration
3. $median_t_{cycle}$	Median cycle duration
4. $mean_t_{onset_to_peak}$	Mean time from onset to systolic peak
5. $std_t_{onset_to_peak}$	Standard deviation of time to systolic peak
6. $median_t_{onset_to_peak}$	Median time to systolic peak
7. $mean_t_{onset_to_notch}$	Mean time from onset to dicrotic notch
8. $std_t_{onset_to_notch}$	Standard deviation of time to dicrotic notch
9. $median_t_{onset_to_notch}$	Median time to dicrotic notch
10. $mean_t_{onset_to_diastolic}$	Mean time from onset to diastolic peak
11. $std_t_{onset_to_diastolic}$	Standard deviation of time to diastolic peak
12. $median_t_{onset_to_diastolic}$	Median time to diastolic peak
13. $mean_t_{delta}$	Mean time difference between diastolic and systolic peaks
14. std_t_{delta}	Standard deviation of time difference
15. $median_t_{delta}$	Median time difference
16. $mean_t_{peak_ratio}$	Mean normalized systolic peak position in cycle
17. $std_t_{peak_ratio}$	Standard deviation of normalized peak position
18. $median_t_{peak_ratio}$	Median normalized peak position
19. $mean_t_{notch_ratio}$	Mean normalized dicrotic notch position in cycle
20. $std_t_{notch_ratio}$	Standard deviation of normalized notch position
21. $median_t_{notch_ratio}$	Median normalized notch position
22. $mean_t_{diastolic_ratio}$	Mean normalized diastolic peak position in cycle
23. $std_t_{diastolic_ratio}$	Standard deviation of normalized diastolic position
24. $median_t_{diastolic_ratio}$	Median normalized diastolic position
25. $mean_amp_{peak}$	Mean systolic peak amplitude
26. std_amp_{peak}	Standard deviation of systolic peak amplitude
27. $median_amp_{peak}$	Median systolic peak amplitude
28. $mean_amp_{notch}$	Mean dicrotic notch amplitude
29. std_amp_{notch}	Standard deviation of notch amplitude
30. $median_amp_{notch}$	Median notch amplitude
31. $mean_amp_{diastolic}$	Mean diastolic peak amplitude
32. $std_amp_{diastolic}$	Standard deviation of diastolic peak amplitude
33. $median_amp_{diastolic}$	Median diastolic peak amplitude
34. $mean_AI$	Mean augmentation index (arterial stiffness indicator)
35. std_AI	Standard deviation of augmentation index
36. $median_AI$	Median augmentation index
37. $mean_RI$	Mean reflection index (diastolic to systolic ratio)
38. std_RI	Standard deviation of reflection index
39. $median_RI$	Median reflection index
40. $mean_SI_{norm}$	Mean normalized stiffness index
41. std_SI_{norm}	Standard deviation of normalized stiffness index
42. $median_SI_{norm}$	Median normalized stiffness index
43. $mean_A_{pulse}$	Mean pulse area (integral under PPG curve)
44. std_A_{pulse}	Standard deviation of pulse area
45. $median_A_{pulse}$	Median pulse area
46. $mean_Skew$	Mean waveform skewness
47. std_Skew	Standard deviation of waveform skewness
48. $median_Skew$	Median waveform skewness

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Feature	Definition
49. <i>mean_Kurt</i>	Mean waveform kurtosis
50. <i>std_Kurt</i>	Standard deviation of waveform kurtosis
51. <i>median_Kurt</i>	Median waveform kurtosis
52. <i>mean_t_rise</i>	Mean rise time (onset to peak)
53. <i>std_t_rise</i>	Standard deviation of rise time
54. <i>median_t_rise</i>	Median rise time
55. <i>mean_t_fall</i>	Mean fall time (peak to notch)
56. <i>std_t_fall</i>	Standard deviation of fall time
57. <i>median_t_fall</i>	Median fall time
PPG Cycle-to-Cycle Variability Features – 8 features	
58. <i>cycle_count</i>	Number of cardiac cycles in segment
59. <i>mean_peak_interval</i>	Mean interval between consecutive peaks (HRV-like)
60. <i>std_peak_interval</i>	Standard deviation of peak intervals
61. <i>cv_peak_interval</i>	Coefficient of variation of peak intervals
62. <i>rmssd_peak_interval</i>	Root mean square of successive differences (HRV metric)
63. <i>mean_amp_diff</i>	Mean amplitude difference between consecutive cycles
64. <i>std_amp_diff</i>	Standard deviation of amplitude differences
65. <i>cv_amp</i>	Coefficient of variation of amplitudes
PPG Frequency-Domain Features – 17 features	
66. <i>dominant_freq</i>	Primary frequency component from FFT
67. <i>dom_freq_mag</i>	Magnitude of primary frequency component
68. <i>second_freq</i>	Second frequency component from FFT
69. <i>second_freq_mag</i>	Magnitude of second frequency component
70. <i>third_freq</i>	Third frequency component from FFT
71. <i>third_freq_mag</i>	Magnitude of third frequency component
72. <i>freq_peak_distance_1_2</i>	Frequency distance between 1st and 2nd peaks
73. <i>freq_peak_distance_1_3</i>	Frequency distance between 1st and 3rd peaks
74. <i>power_vlf</i>	Very low frequency power (0-0.5 Hz)
75. <i>power_lf</i>	Low frequency power (0.5-2.0 Hz, cardiac band)
76. <i>power_hf</i>	High frequency power (2.0-5.0 Hz)
77. <i>power_total</i>	Total spectral power
78. <i>power_lf_norm</i>	Normalized low frequency power
79. <i>power_hf_norm</i>	Normalized high frequency power
80. <i>lf_hf_ratio</i>	Ratio of low to high frequency power
81. <i>spectral_centroid</i>	Spectral centroid frequency
82. <i>spectral_entropy</i>	Normalized spectral entropy
PPG Quality Control Features – 2 features	
83. <i>valid_cycle_count</i>	Number of valid cycles after quality control
84. <i>cycle_rejection_rate</i>	Proportion of cycles rejected by quality control
VPG Aggregated Features (mean/std/median) – 21 features	
85. <i>vpg_vpg_max_mean</i>	Mean of VPG maximum values
86. <i>vpg_vpg_max_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG maximum values
87. <i>vpg_vpg_max_median</i>	Median of VPG maximum values
88. <i>vpg_vpg_min_mean</i>	Mean of VPG minimum values
89. <i>vpg_vpg_min_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG minimum values
90. <i>vpg_vpg_min_median</i>	Median of VPG minimum values
91. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_mean</i>	Mean time of VPG maximum
92. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_std</i>	Standard deviation of time of VPG maximum
93. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_median</i>	Median time of VPG maximum
94. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_mean</i>	Mean time of VPG minimum
95. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_std</i>	Standard deviation of time of VPG minimum

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Feature	Definition
96. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_median</i>	Median time of VPG minimum
97. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_ratio_mean</i>	Mean normalized time position of VPG maximum
98. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of normalized VPG max time
99. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_ratio_median</i>	Median normalized time position of VPG maximum
100. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_ratio_mean</i>	Mean normalized time position of VPG minimum
101. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of normalized VPG min time
102. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_ratio_median</i>	Median normalized time position of VPG minimum
103. <i>vpg_vpg_max_min_ratio_mean</i>	Mean ratio of VPG maximum to minimum
104. <i>vpg_vpg_max_min_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG max/min ratio
105. <i>vpg_vpg_max_min_ratio_median</i>	Median ratio of VPG maximum to minimum
VPG Cycle-to-Cycle Differences – 14 features	
106. <i>vpg_vpg_max_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in VPG maximum between cycles
107. <i>vpg_vpg_max_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG maximum changes
108. <i>vpg_vpg_min_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in VPG minimum between cycles
109. <i>vpg_vpg_min_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG minimum changes
110. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in VPG max time between cycles
111. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG max time changes
112. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in VPG min time between cycles
113. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of VPG min time changes
114. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in normalized VPG max time
115. <i>vpg_vpg_max_time_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of normalized max time changes
116. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in normalized VPG min time
117. <i>vpg_vpg_min_time_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of normalized min time changes
118. <i>vpg_vpg_max_min_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in VPG max/min ratio
119. <i>vpg_vpg_max_min_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of max/min ratio changes
VPG Frequency-Domain Features – 7 features	
120. <i>vpg_dominant_freq</i>	VPG dominant frequency component
121. <i>vpg_dom_freq_mag</i>	VPG dominant frequency magnitude
122. <i>vpg_second_freq</i>	VPG second frequency component
123. <i>vpg_second_freq_mag</i>	VPG second frequency magnitude
124. <i>vpg_freq_peak_distance</i>	VPG frequency peak distance
125. <i>vpg_spectral_entropy</i>	VPG normalized spectral entropy
126. <i>vpg_power_cardiac_band</i>	VPG power in cardiac frequency band (0.5-2 Hz)
APG Aggregated Features (mean/std/median) – 30 features	
127. <i>apg_apg_a_mean</i>	Mean APG wave a (early systolic positive wave)
128. <i>apg_apg_a_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave a
129. <i>apg_apg_a_median</i>	Median APG wave a
130. <i>apg_apg_b_mean</i>	Mean APG wave b (early systolic negative wave)
131. <i>apg_apg_b_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave b
132. <i>apg_apg_b_median</i>	Median APG wave b
133. <i>apg_apg_c_mean</i>	Mean APG wave c (late systolic re-increasing wave)
134. <i>apg_apg_c_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave c
135. <i>apg_apg_c_median</i>	Median APG wave c
136. <i>apg_apg_d_mean</i>	Mean APG wave d (late systolic re-decreasing wave)
137. <i>apg_apg_d_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave d
138. <i>apg_apg_d_median</i>	Median APG wave d
139. <i>apg_apg_e_mean</i>	Mean APG wave e (early diastolic positive wave)
140. <i>apg_apg_e_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave e
141. <i>apg_apg_e_median</i>	Median APG wave e
142. <i>apg_apg_b.a_ratio_mean</i>	Mean ratio of APG wave b to wave a
143. <i>apg_apg_b.a_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of b/a ratio

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Feature	Definition
144. <i>apg_apg_b.a_ratio_median</i>	Median ratio of APG wave b to wave a
145. <i>apg_apg_c.a_ratio_mean</i>	Mean ratio of APG wave c to wave a
146. <i>apg_apg_c.a_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of c/a ratio
147. <i>apg_apg_c.a_ratio_median</i>	Median ratio of APG wave c to wave a
148. <i>apg_apg_d.a_ratio_mean</i>	Mean ratio of APG wave d to wave a
149. <i>apg_apg_d.a_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of d/a ratio
150. <i>apg_apg_d.a_ratio_median</i>	Median ratio of APG wave d to wave a
151. <i>apg_apg_e.a_ratio_mean</i>	Mean ratio of APG wave e to wave a
152. <i>apg_apg_e.a_ratio_std</i>	Standard deviation of e/a ratio
153. <i>apg_apg_e.a_ratio_median</i>	Median ratio of APG wave e to wave a
154. <i>apg_apg_aging_index_mean</i>	Mean APG aging index: $(b - c - d - e)/a$
155. <i>apg_apg_aging_index_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG aging index
156. <i>apg_apg_aging_index_median</i>	Median APG aging index
APG Cycle-to-Cycle Differences – 20 features	
157. <i>apg_apg_a.diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG wave a between cycles
158. <i>apg_apg_a.diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave a changes
159. <i>apg_apg_b.diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG wave b between cycles
160. <i>apg_apg_b.diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave b changes
161. <i>apg_apg_c.diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG wave c between cycles
162. <i>apg_apg_c.diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave c changes
163. <i>apg_apg_d.diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG wave d between cycles
164. <i>apg_apg_d.diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave d changes
165. <i>apg_apg_e.diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG wave e between cycles
166. <i>apg_apg_e.diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of APG wave e changes
167. <i>apg_apg_b.a_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG b/a ratio between cycles
168. <i>apg_apg_b.a_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of b/a ratio changes
169. <i>apg_apg_c.a_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG c/a ratio between cycles
170. <i>apg_apg_c.a_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of c/a ratio changes
171. <i>apg_apg_d.a_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG d/a ratio between cycles
172. <i>apg_apg_d.a_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of d/a ratio changes
173. <i>apg_apg_e.a_ratio_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG e/a ratio between cycles
174. <i>apg_apg_e.a_ratio_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of e/a ratio changes
175. <i>apg_apg_aging_index_diff_mean</i>	Mean change in APG aging index between cycles
176. <i>apg_apg_aging_index_diff_std</i>	Standard deviation of aging index changes
APG Frequency-Domain Features – 7 features	
177. <i>apg_dominant_freq</i>	APG dominant frequency component
178. <i>apg_dom_freq_mag</i>	APG dominant frequency magnitude
179. <i>apg_second_freq</i>	APG second frequency component
180. <i>apg_second_freq_mag</i>	APG second frequency magnitude
181. <i>apg_freq_peak_distance</i>	APG frequency peak distance
182. <i>apg_spectral_entropy</i>	APG normalized spectral entropy
183. <i>apg_power_cardiac_band</i>	APG power in cardiac frequency band (0.5-2 Hz)

2.3.2 Data processing

First, the dataset was split into a training set and a testing set to prevent data leakage during further processing. Table 2 records the class distribution for both the training dataset and the testing dataset. Features 83 and 84 will not be relevant to the hypertension classification task since they are used only to control the quality of the feature extraction process; therefore, they were removed. Missing values were then imputed with the feature’s median per class - at most 5 missing values per feature. Redundancy was subsequently reduced using correlation-based filtering: features with absolute values of correlation larger than 0.9 were removed, leaving 99 features remaining. Afterwards, 24 low-variance features (variance less

than 0.01), features which are not useful in distinguishing between classes and therefore only increase the computational cost of the model later on, were removed. Additionally, outlier capping was implemented via Winsorization, reducing extreme values that are not meaningful physiology. Skewness was also accounted for through Yeo-Johnson Power Transformation. Finally, Robust Scaling was applied because it is more resistant to outliers.

Table 2: Distribution of healthy and hypertensive segments across training and testing subsets - trial 1

Class	Training Subset	Testing Subset	Total Records
Healthy	403,940	12,494	416,434
Hypertensive	47,575	1,471	49,046
Total	451,515	13,965	465,480

2.3.3 Machine Learning and Results

Class weights were computed to account for data imbalance. A logistic regression (L2 regularization, LIBLINEAR solver, maximum iterations of 1000) was trained and tested. Table 3 summarizes the performance of the logistic regression model.

Table 3: Logistic regression performance on hypertension classification - trial 1

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.95	0.70	0.81	12,494
Hypertensive	0.22	0.71	0.34	1,471
Macro Average	0.59	0.71	0.57	–
Weighted Average	0.88	0.70	0.76	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.700			
Balanced Accuracy	0.707			
ROC-AUC Score	0.789			

Random Forest (300 decision trees, no specified maximum depth, the minimum number of samples at leaf node of 5) was also trained and tested to allow non-linear classifying decision boundaries. Table 4 summarizes the performance of the random forest model.

The Random Forest model was subsequently fine-tuned via Grid Search, but the improvement was marginal, sometimes worse. Additionally, a neural network was trained, but its performance was worse than that of the Random Forest.

These results indicate substantial class overlap and weak feature separability.

2.4 Aggregation of clinically validated features

2.4.1 Feature extraction

The second attempt of building the feature matrix was to refer to previous research to identify key features commonly associated with blood pressure. In essence, this article followed the literature review [26] and extracted the 28 features frequently used by other studies to predict blood pressure from PPG.

Table 4: Random forest performance on hypertension classification - trial 1

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.92	0.98	0.95	12,494
Hypertensive	0.63	0.29	0.40	1,471
Macro Average	0.78	0.64	0.68	–
Weighted Average	0.89	0.91	0.89	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.910			
Balanced Accuracy	0.637			
ROC-AUC Score	0.875			

2.4.2 Data processing

Similar to the first approach, the dataset was split into a training set and a testing set, as summarized by table 5. However, since some rows included only NaN values, they were dropped; therefore, the total number of samples became 455320. Furthermore, as these 28 features were reported to correlate with blood pressure, they were not reduced through the correlation and variance methods in trial 1. Nevertheless, they were still processed with Winsorization, Power Transformation, and Robust Scaling as introduced in the previous trial.

Table 5: Distribution of healthy and hypertensive segments across training and testing subsets - trial 2

Class	Training Subset	Testing Subset	Total Records
Healthy	395,401	12,229	407,630
Hypertensive	46,259	1,431	47,690
Total	441,660	13,660	455,320

2.4.3 Machine Learning and Results

Class weights were computed to account for data imbalance. A logistic regression (L2 regularization, LIBLINEAR solver, maximum iterations of 1000) was trained and tested. Table 6 summarizes the performance of the logistic regression model.

Random Forest (300 decision trees, no specified maximum depth, the minimum number of samples at leaf node of 5) was also trained and tested to allow non-linear classifying decision boundaries. Table 7 summarizes the performance of the random forest model.

The Random Forest model was subsequently fine-tuned via Grid Search, but the improvement was marginal, sometimes worse. Additionally, a neural network was trained, but its performance was worse than that of the Random Forest.

These results indicate substantial class overlap and weak feature separability.

3 Analysis and Evaluation

For both trials, each machine learning model performed considerably poorly relative to standard benchmarks for hypertension prediction. Each model suffered an extreme tradeoff between precision and recall for the minority class, despite having class weights implemented, which suggests that the features between the 2 classes severely overlapped with each other. It is not a problem with model complexity as fine-tuning

Table 6: Logistic regression performance on hypertension classification - trial 2

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.95	0.70	0.80	12,229
Hypertensive	0.20	0.66	0.31	1,431
Macro Average	0.57	0.68	0.56	–
Weighted Average	0.87	0.69	0.75	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.690			
Balanced Accuracy	0.678			
ROC-AUC Score	0.749			

Table 7: Random forest performance on hypertension classification - trial 2

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.92	0.97	0.95	12,229
Hypertensive	0.53	0.32	0.40	1,431
Macro Average	0.73	0.64	0.67	–
Weighted Average	0.88	0.90	0.89	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.900			
Balanced Accuracy	0.643			
ROC-AUC Score	0.851			

the random forest and implementing the neural network sometimes yielded worse performance, suggesting overfitting. Upon deeper analysis, not only did some features include a large number of outliers, but they mostly shared a similar distribution. Figures 7 and 8 illustrate this point.

Despite the fact that those features were not discriminant enough to separate the 2 classes, visualizing the PPG signals shows that there are indeed inherent differences in the structure of the PPG wave of a hypertensive record and that of a healthy record. Both figures 9 (mean overlay of 100 randomly chosen samples, 50 samples per class) and 10 (median overlay of 100 randomly chosen samples, 50 samples per class) illustrate that a hypertensive segment differs from a healthy segment by several points: the dicrotic notch, amplitude and height, and time shift. These plots suggest that the current feature extraction methodologies are insufficient in recognizing these important differences and, therefore, fail at distinguishing between the healthy and hypertensive segments.

4 Conclusion

Previously utilized features could not generalize to the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB Database. Given that the 183 features aggregated from literature and the 28 clinically supported, blood-pressure-related features could not differentiate between a healthy segment and a hypertensive segment, although the data suggests that major differences do exist, this implies that finding a universal standard set of discriminant features proves challenging. In essence, a good set of features on one dataset could perform poorly on another. This problem explains the variation between features used across different studies, which is noted by [23]. This standpoint is repeatedly supported by [25]. An important detail to note is that trial 1’s dataset is strictly better than trial 2’s dataset, according to the results, which means there are certain features that are not yet fully explored (in other words, implemented by very few studies) but are potentially more discriminant

Figure 7: Boxplot distribution of diastolic time by class (class 0 = healthy, class 1 = hypertensive).

Figure 8: Histogram distribution of multiple features by class (class 0 = healthy, class 1 = hypertensive).

than current frequently used features.

The implication of this non-universality is that each dataset must undergo a process of examination to establish a dataset-specific optimal set of features, a limitation noted by [11, 21, 23]. A popular way to address this issue is to implement an end-to-end deep learning pipeline that allows a neural network architecture to learn optimal features autonomously [23]. However, these pipelines are usually not interpretable due to the blackbox nature of neural networks, a side-effect of an AI model’s growing complexity [38, 16].

Future research should investigate the specific optimal set of features for the VitalDB dataset or utilize an end-to-end pipeline instead of relying on hand-engineered features. In addition to classification, an alternative approach would be to predict the SBP and DBP of a given PPG signal, a regression task, applying a threshold

Figure 9: Overlay of 100 PPG segments and a plot of the average wave.

Figure 10: Overlay of 100 PPG segments and a plot of the median wave.

to these values based on the definition of hypertension. Finally, future studies can utilize the full expanse of the dataset if they are not limited by physical resources.

References

- [1] “Hypertension.” <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hypertension>.
- [2] “Why is Hypertension a Silent Killer?.” <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/4314-hypertension-high-blood-pressure>.
- [3] S. C. M.Sc., “Photoplethysmography (PPG).” [https://www.news-medical.net/health/Photoplethysmography-\(PPG\).aspx](https://www.news-medical.net/health/Photoplethysmography-(PPG).aspx), July 2016.
- [4] S. R. Tithi, A. Aktar, F. Aleem, and A. Chakrabarty, “ECG data analysis and heart disease prediction using machine learning algorithms,” in *2019 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYP)*, (Kolkata, India), pp. 819–824, IEEE, June 2019.
- [5] Q. Zhang, “Acute ischaemic stroke prediction from physiological time series patterns,” *Australasian Medical Journal*, vol. 6, pp. 280–286, June 2013.
- [6] J. Yu, S. Park, S.-H. Kwon, C. M. B. Ho, C.-S. Pyo, and H. Lee, “AI-Based Stroke Disease Prediction System Using Real-Time Electromyography Signals,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, p. 6791, Sept. 2020.
- [7] R. S. Alkhaldeh, B. Al-Ahmad, A. Ksibi, N. Ghatasheh, E. M. Abu-Taieb, G. Aldehim, M. Ayadi, and S. M. Alkhaldeh, “Convolution Neural Network Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory for Heartbeat Arrhythmia Classification,” *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, vol. 16, p. 197, Dec. 2023.
- [8] Y.-A. Choi, S.-J. Park, J.-A. Jun, C.-S. Pyo, K.-H. Cho, H.-S. Lee, and J.-H. Yu, “Deep Learning-Based Stroke Disease Prediction System Using Real-Time Bio Signals,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, p. 4269, June 2021.
- [9] B. Ballinger, J. Hsieh, A. Singh, N. Sohoni, J. Wang, G. H. Tison, G. M. Marcus, J. M. Sanchez, C. Maguire, J. E. Olgin, and M. J. Pletcher, “DeepHeart: Semi-Supervised Sequence Learning for Cardiovascular Risk Prediction,” 2018.
- [10] K.-J. Butkow, T. Dang, A. Ferlini, D. Ma, and C. Mascolo, “hEARt: Motion-resilient Heart Rate Monitoring with In-ear Microphones,” 2021.
- [11] I. Gotlibovych, S. Crawford, D. Goyal, J. Liu, Y. Kerem, D. Benaron, D. Yilmaz, G. Marcus, and Y. Li, “End-to-end Deep Learning from Raw Sensor Data: Atrial Fibrillation Detection using Wearables,” 2018.
- [12] J. Yu, S. Park, S.-H. Kwon, K.-H. Cho, and H. Lee, “AI-Based Stroke Disease Prediction System Using ECG and PPG Bio-Signals,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 43623–43638, 2022.
- [13] S. Kataria, R. Xiao, T. Ruchti, M. Clark, J. Lu, R. J. Lee, J. Grunwell, and X. Hu, “Continuous Cardiac Arrest Prediction in ICU using PPG Foundation Model,” Feb. 2025.
- [14] T. Sadad, S. A. C. Bukhari, A. Munir, A. Ghani, A. M. El-Sherbeeney, and H. T. Rauf, “Detection of Cardiovascular Disease Based on PPG Signals Using Machine Learning with Cloud Computing,” *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–11, Aug. 2022.
- [15] N. Q. Mahardika T, Y. N. Fuadah, D. U. Jeong, and K. M. Lim, “PPG Signals-Based Blood-Pressure Estimation Using Grid Search in Hyperparameter Optimization of CNN–LSTM,” *Diagnostics*, vol. 13, p. 2566, Aug. 2023.
- [16] J. Chu, W.-T. Yang, Y.-T. Chang, and F.-L. Yang, “Visual Reassessment with Flux-Interval Plot Configuration after Automatic Classification for Accurate Atrial Fibrillation Detection by Photoplethysmography,” *Diagnostics*, vol. 12, p. 1304, May 2022.
- [17] P. Sarkar and A. Etemad, “CardioGAN: Attentive Generative Adversarial Network with Dual Discriminators for Synthesis of ECG from PPG,” Dec. 2020.
- [18] E. Brophy, M. De Vos, G. Boylan, and T. Ward, “Estimation of Continuous Blood Pressure from PPG via a Federated Learning Approach,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, p. 6311, Sept. 2021.

- [19] A. Tazarv and M. Levorato, “A Deep Learning Approach to Predict Blood Pressure from PPG Signals,” July 2021.
- [20] Y. Chu, K. Tang, Y.-C. Hsu, T. Huang, D. Wang, W. Li, S. I. Savitz, X. Jiang, and S. Shams, “Non-invasive arterial blood pressure measurement and SpO₂ estimation using PPG signal: A deep learning framework,” *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, vol. 23, p. 131, July 2023.
- [21] A. Nishan, S. M. Taslim Uddin Raju, M. I. Hossain, S. A. Dipto, S. M. Tanvir Uddin, A. Sijan, M. A. S. Chowdhury, A. Ahmad, and M. Mahamudul Hasan Khan, “A continuous cuffless blood pressure measurement from optimal PPG characteristic features using machine learning algorithms,” *Heliyon*, vol. 10, p. e27779, Mar. 2024.
- [22] H. Mohammadi, B. Tarvirdizadeh, K. Alipour, and M. Ghamari, “Cuff-less blood pressure monitoring via PPG signals using a hybrid CNN-BiLSTM deep learning model with attention mechanism,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, p. 22229, July 2025.
- [23] Y.-C. Hsu, Y.-H. Li, C.-C. Chang, and L. N. Harfiya, “Generalized Deep Neural Network Model for Cuffless Blood Pressure Estimation with Photoplethysmogram Signal Only,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, p. 5668, Oct. 2020.
- [24] D. Pollreisz and N. TaheriNejad, “Detection and Removal of Motion Artifacts in PPG Signals,” *Mobile Networks and Applications*, vol. 27, pp. 728–738, Apr. 2022.
- [25] E. Mejía-Mejía, J. Allen, K. Budidha, C. El-Hajj, P. A. Kyriacou, and P. H. Charlton, “Photoplethysmography signal processing and synthesis,” in *Photoplethysmography*, pp. 69–146, Elsevier, 2022.
- [26] M. Elgendi, E. Jost, A. Alian, R. R. Fletcher, H. Bomberg, U. Eichenberger, and C. Menon, “Photoplethysmography Features Correlated with Blood Pressure Changes,” *Diagnostics*, vol. 14, p. 2309, Oct. 2024.
- [27] L. Frey, C. Menon, and M. Elgendi, “Blood pressure measurement using only a smartphone,” *npj Digital Medicine*, vol. 5, p. 86, July 2022.
- [28] W. Wang, P. Mohseni, K. L. Kilgore, and L. Najafizadeh, “PulseDB: A large, cleaned dataset based on MIMIC-III and VitalDB for benchmarking cuff-less blood pressure estimation methods,” *Frontiers in Digital Health*, vol. 4, p. 1090854, Feb. 2023.
- [29] B. Moody, G. Moody, M. Villarroel, G. Clifford, and I. Silva, “MIMIC-III Waveform Database,” 2017.
- [30] A. Johnson, T. Pollard, and R. Mark, “MIMIC-III Clinical Database,” 2015.
- [31] B. Moody, G. Moody, M. Villarroel, G. Clifford, and I. Silva, “MIMIC-III Waveform Database Matched Subset,” 2017.
- [32] H.-C. Lee and C.-W. Jung, “VitalDB, a high-fidelity multi-parameter vital signs database in surgical patients.”
- [33] Weinan Wang, “PulseDB-Balanced-Training-and-Testing.”
- [34] S. Bagha and L. Shaw, “A Real Time Analysis of PPG Signal for Measurement of SpO₂ and Pulse Rate,” *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 36, pp. 45–50, Dec. 2011.
- [35] Abraham. Savitzky and M. J. E. Golay, “Smoothing and Differentiation of Data by Simplified Least Squares Procedures.,” *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 36, pp. 1627–1639, July 1964.
- [36] P. A. Gorry, “General least-squares smoothing and differentiation by the convolution (Savitzky-Golay) method,” *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 62, pp. 570–573, Mar. 1990.
- [37] W.-H. Lin, X. Li, Y. Li, G. Li, and F. Chen, “Investigating the physiological mechanisms of the photoplethysmogram features for blood pressure estimation,” *Physiological Measurement*, vol. 41, p. 044003, Apr. 2020.
- [38] M. S. Islam, I. Hussain, M. M. Rahman, S. J. Park, and M. A. Hossain, “Explainable Artificial Intelligence Model for Stroke Prediction Using EEG Signal,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, p. 9859, Dec. 2022.